

AFRL

Damage in Textile Compact Compression Specimens: a Numerical and Experimental Study

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1- US Air Force Research Laboratory, USA,

2- U. Dayton Research Institute, USA,

3- Rafael Advanced Defense Systems LTD, Israel,

4- U. Texas at Arlington, USA

5- Israeli Air Force

6- Tel Aviv University

7- U. Massachusetts at Lowell, USA,

US / Israel
Air Vehicle Technology
Project Agreement

- **Overview of collaborative project**
 - Scope and Players
 - Materials & Specimens
 - Testing Description
- **Experimental campaign**
 - Textile Compression Focus
 - Testing Details
 - Selected Results
- **Modeling campaign**
 - Virtual Textile Processing
 - Damage Modeling Methodology
 - Textile FE Methodology
 - Results

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Investigate the effects of **material architecture** and **specimen size** on the **damage evolution** in composite laminates under tension and compression loadings, and develop **numerical methodologies** for its simulation.

- Two types of specimens were chosen for this investigation:

- **OCT for tension**
 - Tested by Israel Team

- **CC for compression**
 - Tested by US Team

Over Height Tension (OCT)*

* Kongshavn and Poursartip (1999)

Compact Compression (CC)**

** Zobeiry et al. (2015)

- Four representative lay-up configurations, of the same resin system (M21 epoxy), were chosen for both the unidirectional (UD) and woven-based laminates:

- Materials purchased by Israeli team

- Panels and specimens manufactured by US team

Layup	UD M21/34%/UD194/IMA-12K	Woven M21/40%/285T2/AS4C-6K
Layup 1a - stacked quasi-isotropic (QI)	$[45/-45/45/-45/0/90/0/90]_{2s}$	$[45/-45/0/90]_{2s}$
Layup 1b - dispersed quasi-isotropic (QI)	$[45/-45/0/90]_{3s}$	$[45/0/-45/90]_{2s}$
Layup 2 - hard (cross-ply)	$[90/0]_{6s}$	$[90/0]_{4s}$
Layup 3 - soft ($\pm 45^\circ$)	$[45/-45]_{6s}$	$[45/-45]_{4s}$

Woven - Twill 2x2

Overview: Specimen Sizes

- Fixture concept and design by Israeli team

Size 2 (smallest)

Size 1 (baseline)

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• Testing Results Summary

- Load-Displacement
- X-ray CT
- Brief comparison to other sizes

• Process-to-Performance Modeling

- Textile architecture virtual processing
- Tow-level global-local FE model

Woven - Twill 2x2

• Carbon fiber composite panels

- Unidirectional (UD): Hexply M21/34%/UD194/IMA-12k
- Woven (2x2 twill): Hexply M21/40%/285T2/AS4C-6k

• All Stacking Sequences

- except 1a for largest size

• 8 samples water jet cut for each

• Instrumentation

- MTS electromechanical frame
- 3-dimensional digital image correlation (DIC)
- Extensometer for displacement
- Acoustic emission
- X-ray computed tomography (ex situ)

• Types of tests

1. Modified compliance calibration (x1)
2. Total failure (x2 or 3)
3. Interrupted at first acoustic emission signal (x1)
4. Interrupted at 90% average peak load (x1)
5. Interrupted at first load drop (x1)
6. Interrupted at second load drop (x1)

Compression

- Normalized by specimen thickness

Load-displacement curves for all sizes

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Compression

- Data for sizes 2 and 3 were scaled up and down by $\sqrt{2}$, respectively, based in LEFM assumptions

- Larger specimens fail more abruptly and at higher normalized loads, for all layups

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----- Smallest (size 2) Specimens -----

90% Peak Load

First Load Drop

Final Load

----- First Load Drop -----

S2 - Small

S1 - Medium

S3 - Large

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Multi-Chain Digital Element Method

5-module software suite

Rx-FEM

- AFRL-unique methodology
- Captures matrix crack discontinuity
- Preserves integration schema
 - cracks & delams behave well numerically!

larve, E.V. and Mollenhauer, D.H., "Chapter 9: Mesh-Independent Matrix Cracking and Delamination Modeling in Advanced Composite Materials," *Numerical Modelling of Failure in Advanced Composite Materials*, 1st Edition, editors Pedro Camanho and Stephen Hallett, Woodhead Publishing, August 2015.

larve, E., Hoos, K., Braginsky, M., Zhou, E., and Mollenhauer, D., "Progressive Failure Simulation in Laminated Composites Under Fatigue Loading by using Discrete Damage Modeling," *Journal of Composite Materials*, 51(15): 2143-2161, 2017.

Initiation (Matrix Damage)

- LaRC-04 for matrix cracks {NASA}
- Hashin-Rotem + Miner Rule for fatigue
 - matrix cracks & delamination {AFRL}

Propagation (Matrix Damage) {AFRL}

- Cohesive Zone Method for static & fatigue
- CZM "release pressure" changed when Miner Rule accumulates enough damage (see below)

Initiation/Propagation (Fiber Damage)

- Critical Failure Volume (stochastic) {AFRL}
- Continuum Damage Mechanics {mod. NASA}

Fatigue

- ΔN_c – insertion of new transverse matrix crack
- ΔN_l – initiation of delamination CZM damage

- ΔN_p – CZM damage progression of one interval

- C, m – material constants
- d_1 – damage "history" variable

Fatigue Damage Initiation

("Palmgren-Miner" Strength)

- Delamination & RX-FEM crack
- $$\Delta N_c = \min \left[(1 - d_l^q) / \Delta N_{Limit}^{q+1} \right]$$
- $$\Delta N_l = \min \left[(1 - d_l^q) / \Delta N_{Limit}^{q+1} \right]$$

Fatigue Damage Propagation

- Modified Paris Law
- $$da/dN = C(G_{max}/G_C)^m$$
- Extension by one element
- $$\Delta N_p = l_e / C(G_{max}/G_C)^m$$

2D Illustration

2D Illustration

3D Illustration

Shown here (example weave):

- Produce a textile preform layer
- Duplicate and rotate
- Bring layers together

Not shown:

- Compact with platen and/or virtual vacuum bag
- Trim to size
- Extract surfaces around tows and mesh tows individually

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- **IMM FE Model in BSAM**

- Global-local approach
- Homogenized outer regions
- Uni properties in tows
- M-21 epoxy properties in matrix surrounding tows

- **Tetrahedral Elements**

- Pins & Homogenized Regions
- Tows
- 2nd order elements

- **Hexahedral Elements**

- Matrix
- Sectioned via IMM procedures

- **Boundary Conditions**

- Symmetry on back face
- Pin front face displaced vertically and restricted horizontally

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Preliminary Modeling: Damage Extent at First Load Drop **AFRL**

- Purple = fiber damage
- Red = tow transverse cracks

note: compare to both

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- Purple = fiber damage
- Red = tow transverse cracks
- Gold = matrix cracking

• Observations

- Fiber damage in prediction shows similar morphology and extent as experiment
- Transverse matrix cracking in simulation results extends beyond that observed in experiment
- Tow-tow and Tow-matrix delamination more extensive in simulation than experiment (not shown here)
- Experimentally observed damage extent on surface plies is more extensive than internal plies, tending to buckle out-of-plane
- Potentially necessary to use geometrically non-linear solutions to capture out-of-plane surface effects

**delamination not shown for clarity*

- **Joint experimental/numerical study**
 - Progressive damage testing across scales and architectures
 - Tension and compression
 - Divided responsibilities, great coordination/cooperation
- **ICME for textile laminate simulation demonstrated**
 - Integrated computational materials engineering
 - Textile preform virtual processing
 - Progressive damage model using “as-processed” architectures
- **Reasonable simulation results**
 - Excellent agreement between virtually processed architecture and actual specimen architecture
 - Good agreement on load-displacement behavior
 - Simulated damage patterns and extents compare favorably with experiment with exception of more widespread transverse matrix & delamination predictions

Questions

